

Developing future primary school teachers' communication through pedagogy of partnership

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ABSTRACT

The study of the role of the pedagogy of partnership (PoP) in building the professional competence of future primary school teachers is relevant in the context of modern educational and pedagogical transformations, which require the preparation of teachers for new challenges and creating a favourable learning environment. Therefore, the aim of our study was to check the effect of observing the pedagogical partnership principles in the educational process on the development of the communicative competence of future primary school teachers. The study employed the following psychodiagnostic methods: the Thomas-Kilmann conflict mode instrument (TKI), Myers-Briggs type indicator (MBTI), Snyder's self-control in communication. The implementation of the PoP programme in higher education institutions (HEIs) has a positive effect on the development of the communicative competence of future teachers, in particular, on developing the ability for self-control and increasing the scope of psychological knowledge. The study revealed some important correlations. Our results indicate that cooperation and the ability to make compromises are directly related to the communicative abilities of future teachers. Further research can be focused on studying the impact of pedagogical partnership on other aspects of future teacher training, such as methodical mastery, motivation for learning and development.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The introduction of pedagogical partnership in Ukraine is connected with the implementation of the concept of the new Ukrainian school [1]. This concept involves transitioning from the traditional education model to a new approach aimed at active interaction and cooperation of all participants in the educational process. Because of the importance of pedagogical partnership in modern educational practice, it appears that successful learning and development of future teachers largely depend on proper interaction between all participants in the educational process. Cooperation between future teachers, students, parents and other

stakeholders is key to creating a favourable learning environment. The pedagogical partnership covers such aspects as joint planning and evaluation of education, involvement of parents in the educational process, openness to new ideas and innovations, and development of effective communication between all participants. It is important to emphasize that the pedagogical partnership contributes to developing future teachers' competence and improving the quality of education, creating a favourable educational atmosphere [2], [3].

The main task of the research is to determine the influence of the principles of pedagogical partnership in the educational process on the ability of future primary school teachers to communicate. The pedagogical partnership is a key factor in creating a favorable educational environment in implementing the new Ukrainian school (NUS) concept, which involves transitioning from the traditional education model to active interaction and cooperation of all participants in the educational process. The growing role of interaction between future teachers, students, parents and other people involved in the educational process requires researchers to study the practical experience of pedagogical partnership and evaluate its effectiveness. In particular, the research should focus on whether adherence to the principles of pedagogical partnership contributes to the development of communicative competence in students preparing to become future primary school teachers. Therefore, the aim of this study is to determine whether observance of the pedagogical partnership principles in the educational process affects the development of communicative competence of future primary school teachers. The research hypothesis assumes that the introduction of pedagogical partnership in the educational process of a higher school contributes to the development of communicative competence of future primary school teachers and promotes the development of the optimal type of social behaviour in conflict situations. The main objectives arising from the relevance of the issue under research are to: i) study the practical experience of implementing pedagogical partnership in the educational process of a higher school and evaluate its effectiveness; ii) check whether the development of communicative competence among students contributes to the development of the type of social behaviour in conflict situations that is optimal for pedagogical activity; iii) determine whether there are correlations between different scales of communicative competence of future primary school teachers.

The pedagogy of partnership (PoP) in the context of the development of the professional competence of future primary school teachers is an urgent current issue [4]. Pedagogical partnership is a concept based on the joint activity and interaction of various participants in the educational process with the aim of achieving common goals and improving the quality of education [5]. This approach is based on mutually beneficial cooperation, mutual understanding, respect and mutual trust between all participants [6]. The concept of pedagogical partnership includes approaches that promote interaction between a teacher and a student, combining the principles of active student involvement, inclusive learning and democratic methods of learning and interaction [7], [8]. Partnership pedagogy also reflects a positive approach to peace, seeing it as more than just the absence of conflict and war [9], [10]. This pedagogical approach is also known as collaborative pedagogy [11].

The basis of partnership pedagogy is the humane attitude of the teacher to children, which involves respect for their thoughts and wishes [12]. In the PoP, students become active participants in the learning process, while teachers act as mediators, facilitators, and mentors [13], [14]. Pedagogical partnership involves different stakeholders such as teachers, students, parents, school administration, community, and other stakeholders [15]. Each of these parties has its own goals, expectations and resources, and they work together to achieve the best possible outcomes in teaching students [16].

The PoP is based on voluntariness, equality, democracy, and respect for the individual within established norms, rules, requirements, and responsibilities [17]. Each party supports and promotes active cooperation while fulfilling joint educational tasks, confirming each party's responsibility for the results achieved [18]. One of the main peculiarities of the PoP is the active role of future teachers in the educational process [19]. They become co-creators of learning, actively interact with students and consider their individual needs and interests. This active interaction promotes the development of communication skills, empathy, and the ability to adapt to different learning situations. This is the atmosphere where all students feel heard and important [20].

The PoP also emphasizes the importance of interaction with students' parents. Future teachers learn to collaborate with parents, listen to their views, and consider their expectations for their child's learning [21], [22]. The PoP promotes the development of teachers' reflection and self-control skills. They learn to analyze their work, improve their teaching methods and strategies based on joint discussion and feedback with students and other participants in the learning process [23]. The PoP is also used to enhance students' interest in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) subjects [24], [25]. The main forms of work provided by the PoP are proposed as shown in Figure 1 based on academic literature and guidelines [26]–[28].

Figure 1. Basic forms of work provided by the PoP in HEIs

2. METHODS AND MATERIALS

2.1. Research design

The study was organized in three stages from February 2023 to October 2023. The first preparatory stage included: selection, substantiation and theoretical understanding of the issue under research; development of a programme for the implementation of the PoP into the educational process of HEIs, guidelines, methods of conducting an experiment. The second main stage included: experimental measurement of the components of future teachers' communicative competence; implementation of the pedagogical partnership programme in the HEIs; conducting post-experimental measurement. The third final stage included: data processing, interpretation of statistical indicators; comparison of the obtained results with the expected ones; development of recommendations and preparation of the research results.

2.2. Sample

The experiment was conducted at Vinnytsia Mykhailo Kotsiubynskyi State Pedagogical University. As of the beginning of the 2021/2022 academic year, 16,804 people studied full-time in Ukraine at the first (Bachelor) level of the major 013: primary education, which made up the general population of the sample (Higher and Professional Pre-Higher Education in Ukraine in 2021: statistics, 2022). After calculating the size of the required (representative) sample using an online calculator (with parameters: confidence probability 95%, margin of error 5%), the size of the valid sample was 379 people. This number was the starting point for forming two experimental groups (EG) ($n_1 = 134$, $n_2 = 134$) and two control groups (CG) ($n_1=130$, $n_2=134$). The experiment involved students of the 3rd and 4th years of study. The experimental data of each team were tested for normality of distribution using the one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test λ .

2.3. Methods

The Thomas-Kilmann conflict mode instrument (TKI). A method that allows you to determine how a person interacts in conflict situations. Participants can be classified into five conflict styles using the TKI. It allows you to assess their readiness and ability to resolve conflicts in the educational environment effectively. Myers-Briggs type indicator (MBTI) software is based on the concepts of psychological types developed by Myers and Briggs. The personality characteristics of the participants, including their style of perceiving and processing information, can be determined using the MBTI, which is important for understanding their communication style. Snyder's self-control in communication. The tool allows you to measure self-control and a person's reaction in communication. Given the importance of communication's emotional and social aspects, this technique helps assess how effectively participants can manage their emotions and reactions during communication.

2.4. Instruments

Diagnostic methods were placed in the students' personal account in the Moodle system. Each participant of the experiment was sent instructions on how to undergo diagnostics. The SPSS 17.0 package was used for statistical data processing. The dependencies between communicative and organizational abilities and behaviour styles in conflict situations of future primary school teachers were identified using the correlation method according to the Pearson's chi-squared test (r). The student's t-test was used to compare

the values between the two experimental groups at the beginning and end of the experiment for each component of communicative competence.

2.5. Ethical criteria

The respondents' participation in the study was voluntary, the principles of protecting the rights of research participants, ensuring their safety and data privacy were observed in the data collection process. The research was built on the principles of impartiality and objectivity. Respondents freely chose whether to participate in the study, which emphasizes the importance of informed and voluntary consent. This approach ensures that subjects are fully informed about the study's aims, processes and potential consequences before they decide to participate. The research was conducted in compliance with ethical rules designed to protect the rights of all research participants. This included being openly informed about the purpose of the study, the freedom to withdraw at any time without penalty, and assurances that their participation would not jeopardize their academic or professional status.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the beginning of the pedagogical experiment, initial testing of communicative competence was carried out among the EG and CG participants with the identification of the level of each component criterion of communicative competence. For this purpose, we used Snyder's self-control in communication. The obtained results indicate that there were no significant differences in the studied indicators in the CG and EG participants at the beginning of the experiment as shown in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. The level of components of communicative competence in EG students ($x \pm y$), point*

Indicator of communicative competence	EG	Stage of the experiment		P ₀
		Beginning	End	
Communication abilities	n ₁	1.5 ± 0.12	1.8 ± 0.08	> 0.05
	n ₂	1.6 ± 0.13	1.9 ± 0.05	> 0.05
Communication skills	n ₁	1.8 ± 0.50	2.7 ± 0.49	< 0.01
	n ₂	2.0 ± 0.41	2.6 ± 0.32	< 0.01
The scope of psychological knowledge	n ₁	1.0 ± 0.15	2.4 ± 0.21	< 0.01
	n ₂	1.4 ± 0.20	2.3 ± 0.20	< 0.01
Self-control ability	n ₁	1.0 ± 0.01	2.3 ± 0.04	< 0.01
	n ₂	1.3 ± 0.02	2.4 ± 0.05	< 0.01
Personality traits	n ₁	1.3 ± 0.02	1.8 ± 0.02	< 0.05
	n ₂	1.2 ± 0.01	1.7 ± 0.03	< 0.05

Note: n₁-the result of the first group; n₂-the result of the second group

Table 2. The level of components of communicative competence in CG students ($x \pm y$), point*

Indicator of communicative competence	EG	Stage of the experiment		P ₀
		Beginning	End	
Communication abilities	n ₁	1.5 ± 0.12	1.7 ± 0.14	> 0.05
	n ₂	1.6 ± 0.13	1.8 ± 0.15	> 0.05
Communication skills	n ₁	2.0 ± 0.41	2.2 ± 0.43	> 0.05
	n ₂	2.1 ± 0.42	2.3 ± 0.44	> 0.05
The scope of psychological knowledge	n ₁	1.4 ± 0.20	1.6 ± 0.22	> 0.05
	n ₂	1.5 ± 0.21	1.7 ± 0.23	> 0.05
Self-control ability	n ₁	1.3 ± 0.02	1.5 ± 0.04	> 0.05
	n ₂	1.4 ± 0.03	1.6 ± 0.05	> 0.05
Personality traits	n ₁	1.2 ± 0.01	1.4 ± 0.03	> 0.05
	n ₂	1.3 ± 0.02	1.5 ± 0.04	> 0.05

The post-experimental measurement of the level of communicative competence of future teachers Table 1 showed significant changes occurred in the development of communicative competence in both experimental groups: in the first group the average score increased by 8 points, in the second group it increased by 14 points. There were no positive changes in the level of communicative competence in the control groups showed in Table 2. Of the five registered indicators of communicative competence in the experimental groups of future primary school teachers, only the indicator of communicative abilities did not show a reliable increase. This testifies to their conservatism and difficulties in building communicative competence. In the experimental group, the greatest increase was found: in the self-control ability from 1.0 points to 2.3 points in the first group and from 1.3 points to 2.4 points in the second group ($p < 0.01$); in the

scope of psychological knowledge from 1.0 points to 2.4 points in the first group and from 1.4 points to 2.3 points in the second group ($p < 0.01$). Insignificant growth rates were observed during the formation of personality traits.

Human behaviour in conflict situations manifests itself in five known types: rivalry, cooperation, compromise, conflict avoidance, adjustment. Each person chooses a particular style of behaviour in a particular situation. In our opinion, it is determined both by the personal qualities of an individual and by the level of communicative competence. In our study, we assumed that the development of communicative competence in future teachers will contribute to their development of the type of social behaviour in conflict situations that is optimal for pedagogical activity. So, we tested the type of social behaviour according to the TKI method at the beginning and end of the pedagogical experiment as shown in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3. The predominant type of social behaviour in a conflict situation among EG and CG students at the beginning of the experiment (%)

Groups	Type of social behaviour in a conflict situation					
	Rivalry	Cooperation	Compromise	Avoidance	Adjustment	
EG	n ₁	31	17	20	17	15
	n ₂	29	18	22	15	16
CG	n ₁	30	18	19	17	16
	n ₂	28	20	20	15	17

Table 4. The predominant type of social behaviour in a conflict situation among EG and CG students at the end of the experiment (%)

Groups	Type of social behaviour in a conflict situation					
	Rivalry	Cooperation	Compromise	Avoidance	Adjustment	
EG	n ₁	11	37	25	17	10
	n ₂	17	31	20	15	17
CG	n ₁	28	20	20	16	16
	n ₂	30	20	18	14	18

Before the pedagogical experiment, rivalry was the predominant type of social behaviour among students, which, in our opinion, is characteristic of students studying to become teachers. This desire is also manifested in the preference for competition in social behaviour. After the end of the experiment, most of the EG students became oriented towards cooperation and compromise in their behaviour. So, the development of communicative competence made it possible to reorient the EG participants to the optimal type of social behaviour for their future professional and pedagogical activities cooperation. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was used to identify the relationships between communicative and organizational abilities, which were assessed using the MBTI method, and behaviour styles in conflict situations of future primary school teachers, the correlation method. The main results are given in Table 5.

Table 5. Correlations between scales of communicative competence of future primary school teachers of EG

Correlation	Correlation coefficient (r)	Significance level (p)
Cooperation↔Communication abilities	0.39	$p < 0.05$
Avoidance↔Adjustment	-0.39	$p < 0.05$
Adjustment↔Organizational abilities	0.57	$p < 0.05$
Compromise↔Cooperation	0.57	$p < 0.05$
Communication abilities↔Organizational abilities	0.94	$p < 0.05$
Compromise↔Rivalry	-0.63	$p < 0.05$
Organizational abilities↔Rivalry	-0.44	$p < 0.05$
Communication abilities↔Adjustment	-0.31	$p < 0.05$

Correlation analysis of the results of the research on the communicative competence of future teachers, which is based on the correlation method according to the (r), revealed the significance of the correlation at two levels: at the level of $p \leq 0.01$ and at the level of $p \leq 0.05$. A direct correlation was established between cooperation and communication abilities ($r = 0.39$, $p < 0.05$). Therefore, if future teachers strive to establish interpersonal contacts, thereby realizing their communicative abilities, they have a greater chance of finding ways to interact and collaborate with students. The relationship on the avoidance and adjustment scales ($r = -0.39$, $p < 0.05$) is inversely proportional, which demonstrates the corresponding dependence of these scales as a situation when the greater the future teachers strive to adapt to the conditions of communication with

students, the less they avoid this communication, the greater the desire to create and maintain this interaction. A number of other direct correlations were also found between the following scales: adjustment and organizational abilities ($r = 0.57$, $p < 0.05$). This dependence shows the better the future teacher fulfils the duties of an organizer, knows how to involve students in activities and cooperation, can organize the students' performance of tasks during and after the lesson, the easier he/she can adapt to new circumstances, the easier it is for him/her to give up some of his interests for the sake of common affairs, studies.

The compromise scale is directly correlated with the cooperation scale ($r = 0.57$, $p < 0.05$) for future teachers. The compromise involves settling differences with the opponent through mutual concessions. The more a person (future teacher) can make concessions, the friendlier the interaction becomes. A direct relationship was also found between the communicative abilities scale and the organizational abilities scale ($r = 0.94$, $p < 0.05$). With effective communication skills, which are realized in the ability to communicate with students, convey educational information and build knowledge through discussions and discussions of topics, organizational skills become extremely important. They help to systematize, organize and effectively present information in the educational process. The revealed direct correlations emphasize the role of ethical and moral norms and values in the emergence and development of communicative competence in future primary school teachers.

Inverse correlations were also found. For example, an inverse relationship was found between the compromise and rivalry scales ($r = -0.63$, $p < 0.05$). In the event that the future teacher shows a tendency to make compromises (albeit mutual, but still concessions), this does not contribute to the competitive type of behaviour, which involves active competition and efforts to improve communication. An indirect relationship was also found between the scale's organizational abilities and competition ($r = -0.44$, $p < 0.05$). The less the future teacher has the ability to organize educational activities, the more his/her students strive to achieve personal success in the learning process and engage in struggle, worrying only about their own interests. There is also an inverse correlation between the communication abilities and adjustment scales ($r = -0.31$, $p < 0.05$). A high level of communication skills among future teachers absolutely reduces the need for behaviour aimed at making compromises that is, agreeing to make concessions in the educational process.

The obtained results give grounds to state that the introduction of the principles of the PoP into the educational process of a higher school has a positive effect on the development of communicative competence of future primary school teachers, in particular on the development of the self-control and the ability to increase the scope of psychological knowledge. This can be confirmed by the fact that in the process of implementing PoP, teachers use new democratic forms of interaction and teaching methods. The development of communicative competence made it possible to reorient future EG teachers to the optimal type of social behaviour for their future professional and pedagogical activities cooperation. The hypothesis of our research was confirmed.

Our conclusions are consistent with the research of other authors in the field of pedagogical partnership. Levchyk *et al.* [5] confirms that partnerships between teachers, students, and parents contribute to the development of stable competencies. Barrie and Pizzica [29] indicate the effectiveness of the PoP in STEM education, which can also be applied in the preparation of future primary school teachers. Woolmer *et al.* [30], and Zhuravlova *et al.* [31] emphasize that the PoP is an effective tool for achieving educational goals, in particular in the form of active and voluntary interaction of participants in the educational process.

The study found a number of important correlations. Our results indicate that cooperation and the ability to make compromises are interrelated with the communicative abilities of future teachers. This means that the introduction of the principles of the PoP into the educational process of a higher school contributes to the improvement of communication skills and the ability to avoid conflicts in the future. This is also explained by the change in the teacher's role not as a deliverer of knowledge, but as a partner, a coach [32]. Instead, the study's results by Abramov [33] express justified concerns about the effectiveness of partnerships in higher education. The study's authors note that comparing the pedagogical conditions of the partnership with the pedagogical conditions of a regular educational environment did not yield statistically significant results. Of course, it may also be related to the research methodology used and existing methodological, instrumental, and other limitations.

The study also showed that organizational abilities and the ability to adapt to different communication conditions are interdependent. Future teachers who successfully organize educational activities and involve students in cooperation, adapt more easily to new situations and are ready to adapt to different circumstances. This interaction between organizational and communicative abilities indicates the integrated nature of the future teachers' competence development. Nurshaikhova *et al.* [34] also concluded that the PoP gave an impetus to the creative activity of many teachers, initiated the activity of author schools.

The significant relationship between the compromise and cooperation indicates that future teachers who are more inclined to make compromises also show a tendency for joint and friendly interaction. This is

also confirmed by the theoretical findings in [35]. This can be important in creating a favourable learning environment and enhancing student motivation. This also confirms the opinion of [36], that Ukraine is currently on a difficult path to establishing democratic values. The identified relationship between communicative abilities and organizational abilities indicates the importance of effective communication in the educational process. Future teachers with a high level of communication skills proved to be better at organizing educational activities during practice, which can positively affect the effectiveness of learning.

3.1. Research limitations

The main limiting factor of the study is a limited period of the experimental work (one semester). Only full-time students participated in the experimental study. The main limitation of this study is the short time period of only one semester. A longer duration may provide a deeper understanding of the ongoing impact of partnership pedagogy on the development of communication skills of future primary school teachers. Only full-time students participated in the study. The results may not capture all the variation that can occur when students participate in part-time or non-traditional forms of education. Future studies should consider diversifying the participants to make the study more unique.

3.2. Recommendations

For further development of the raised problem, we recommend expanding the experimental study with the involvement of future teachers of other majors. To increase the reliability of the study, it is recommended to expand the circle of participants beyond the limits of candidates for the position of primary school teacher. Including future teachers from different specialties and educational levels will provide a broader perspective on the impact of pedagogical partnerships on communicative competence. This approach can contribute to a more complete understanding of how partnership pedagogy affects different educational contexts.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The PoP becomes a key factor in the successful training of future primary school teachers in the current educational context, where the emphasis is on the development of activity, independence and critical thinking. In such an environment, future teachers are actively involved in the educational process and build meaningful learning together with teachers. The implementation of the principles of PoP in the educational process is a significant factor contributing to the improvement of the development of communicative competence of future primary school teachers. This conclusion is based on objective evidence and research results, which indicate the positive impact of pedagogical partnership on developing communicative abilities, skills, psychological knowledge, self-control and personality traits of future teachers. Implementing the principles of the PoP involves active interaction between teachers, students, and parents of future teachers. This approach helps to change the traditional teacher's role as a deliverer of knowledge to the role of a partner who builds knowledge together with students. Such joint activity encourages teachers to search for new forms of interaction and teaching methods.

The obtained results can be used in HEIs to support the development of pedagogical partnerships and in professional development programmes for teachers to improve their qualifications. These results can also become the basis for further research and the development of new methodologies and approaches to training future primary school teachers. Promising directions for further research are the impact of pedagogical partnership on other aspects of training future teachers, such as methodological skills, motivation for learning and development.

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